

**THE INSTRUCTIONAL MATERIALS OF
THE ARABIC LANGUAGE TEACHING FOR NON-ARABIC
SPEAKERS IN THE REPUBLIC OF INDONESIA: A TYPICAL STUDY
OF THE STATE UNIVERSITY OF MALANG, INDONESIA**

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Abstract:

The aim of this research work is to identify the extent of the effectiveness of the Instructional Materials in teaching of the Arabic Language at the State University of Malang in Indonesia. Meanwhile, the two researchers have chosen the State University of Malang in Indonesia as a case study because it is one of the renowned universities in Indonesia and as it takes much interest in Arabic Language Education. Therefore, both researchers evaluated the Arabic Language Instructional Materials adopted in the State University of Malang, Indonesia under the light of Communication Approach in the Arabic Teaching Language where they distributed questionnaires to the teachers of the university concerned in order to get facts on the content about the Arabic Language Instructional Materials therein, then they analyzed them through quantitative and evaluative methods for the purpose of achieving the rightly desired outcome. The Communication Approach in the teaching Arabic for Non-Native Speakers observes that Arabic language is a communication means, and it is necessary that its teaching be made for this purpose. Therefore, the existence of the suitable Instructional Materials which can empower students on the communication skills in Arabic language is a very important issue in the teaching of Arabic language under the light of this approach. Thus, this research paper is a quantitative evaluative work as it exploits quantitative method to identify some facts about the proper instructional materials for Arabic Language Teaching at the State University of Malang in Indonesia from a widest and comprehensive perspective (Obserne, 1977). As for the evaluative method, it has been adopted for the purpose of rendering an accurate objective ruling, on some approaches, processes and products. Consequently, the areas of strengths and weakness are identifiable to facilitate the adoption of suitable resolutions that can rectify the detected points of weakness and failure (Yusuf, 1962). The research has consequently arrived at an outcome that the positive sides of the instructional materials for the Arabic Language teaching in the State University of Malang in Indonesia are visibly apparent as it is grossly equipped with various (audio-visual) teaching aids. Likewise, the

majority of the teachers are highly interested in using them during the teaching process, because of its perfection, development and enhanced effectiveness, in addition to the availability of a number of teachers who are well-versed in using them. In regard to the negative sides, it is obviously seen in the manner of oversight of small number of them while using the materials during Arabic Language Teaching. This negative side should be improved in order to acquaint all the teachers of that university with the application of various teaching aids in the teaching procedures, in addition to a big number among them who are not well-versed in using them to some extent. That is a weak side of it which should be improved so as to achieve perfection in Arabic Language teaching at that university in a better way. Likewise, some instruments adopted in the instructional materials are outdated and need to be rectified.

Keywords: instructional, materials, Arabic, language, teaching

1. Introduction

Teaching is an art which includes knowledge, presentation, an art of dissemination and above all every aspect of paralinguistic. Teaching demands broad knowledge of subject matter in all horizons, complete curriculum with standards, positive and caring attitude with enthusiasm, and a desire for learning and techniques of classroom management and a desire to make a difference in the lives of young people. The existence of materials is totally based on the creativity and innovative ways of teachers. No one can assume even a single material without a Teacher because it is a teacher who uses the materials in the classroom effectively and the effective usage of those materials is reflected by the involvement of the students ([Shravan Kumar](#), 2017).

2. Literature Review

2.1. Teaching Aids and Teaching Materials

Material used by a teacher to supplement classroom instruction or to stimulate the interest of students (<http://www.dictionary.com/browse/teaching-aid?s=t>), and teaching aid is an object (such as a book, picture, or map) or device (such as a DVD or computer) used by a teacher to enhance or enliven classroom instruction (<http://www.dictionary.com/browse/teaching-aid?s=t>).

- Mechanical aids.

B. What are teaching materials?

Teaching materials are the materials which the teacher can use to help students learn a foreign language through visual or audio perception. They must be capable of contributing to the achievement of the practical, cultural, and educational aims of learning a foreign language. Good teaching materials will help greatly to reinforce the students' initial desire to learn the language and to sustain their enthusiasm throughout the course (<https://canvas.instructure.com/courses/885965/pages/teaching-aids-and-teaching-materials-in-flt>).

2.2. Teaching Materials and Teaching Aids: Role of Teacher

Teacher is the driver of the classroom who drives the class as per his pace and desire. He makes an environment in which all the students delve themselves in the ocean of knowledge which happens due to usage of the materials and aids used by the teacher in the classroom. They use themselves as an aid when they start using facts as a starting point and ask "why" questions and then look at all sides and encourage students to predict what will happen next. As a material, they try to engage the whole class with their questions and with the help of their motivation and varied questions they make a live classroom where every student gets involved.

William Arthur Ward rightly says, "*The mediocre teacher tells. The good teacher explains. The superior teacher demonstrates. The great teacher inspires*" (http://www.goodreads.com/author/show/416931.William_Arthur_Ward). This quote reveals that teacher is an aid who changes himself according to the desired situation for facilitating and motivating the students in a better way.

Dr Seuss says, "*You have brains in your head. You have feet in your shoes. You can steer yourself in any direction you choose. You're on your own, and you know what you know. And you are the guy who'll decide where to go.*" (<https://www.goodreads.com/quotes/22842-you-have-brains-in-your-head-you-have-feet-in>).

According to Kumar (2017), as soon as teacher enters in the classroom, he starts using materials which already exist in the classroom. He starts talking about last classes which gives a platform to the students for getting out something and teacher tries to link up that interaction with his/her upcoming class and it becomes a material for a teacher. A teacher digs out the material from the classroom and uses accordingly. Like, Students were scolded by a teacher of last class and a language teacher can ask few students to come up and share the experience of last class and from there that language teacher tries to hone the speaking skills of the students. These materials can be used to chisel the speaking skills of the students and students will be speaking whole heartedly, which can be a good material to be used by any language teaching specialist. Teacher can use himself to project anything in a better way by his gestures, postures, facial expressions and voice. For example, a teacher can teach the presentation strategies to

the students by his voice modulation and facial expressions. It is the power of speech that may turn a dull topic into an interesting one whereas poor delivery may spoil significant presentation. So once the speaker has planned and developed the content he should begin practicing because it is not important what to say as it is how to say. There are a variety of delivery methods. A speech with same pitch delivered with stating pitch becomes monotonous so there should be variation in a pitch. The voice should be well modulated with proper pause at the right place along with normal rate of speech and fillers should be avoided. It can be easily practiced by these materials used by teacher in the classroom. We express our emotions through words but often the feel of emotion is expressed through our various body parts. We can communicate by nodding our head, blinking our eyes, shrugging our shoulders or working our hands. When we study body language, we look at the symbols of meaning that the physical movements of the body are communicating. Through body students when they observe their teacher in the classroom and try to imitate the teacher.

2.3. Guidelines for Teaching and Learning Materials

Littlejohn and Windeatt (1989) says, *“Materials have a hidden curriculum that includes attitudes toward knowledge, attitudes toward teaching and learning, attitudes toward the role and relationship of the teacher and student, and values and attitudes related to gender, society, etc. Materials have a basic instructional viewpoint, approach, method, and content, including which provide linguistic and cultural information.”*

As Jolly and Bolitho (1988) write, *“Materials should also be contextualised to the experiences, movements true inner conditions are reflected. For the expression of these inner body states faces, eyes, gestures & physical appearance are to be studied. For self-control, the presenter should pay attention to his body language. These things can be easily learnt by the realities and first languages of the learners. An important part of this involves awareness on the part of the teacher-designer of the “socio-cultural appropriacy” of things such as the designer’s own style of presenting material, of arranging groups, and so on. So, it is required to inform about the culture-specific learning processes of the proposed learners. Materials should be interlinked by which learner can acquaint him with the materials. The materials should be based on the experiences and realities which should be related to the topics and it should be appropriate for the desired learner to make sure of their involvement.”*

Hall D. (1995) also says, *“Most people who learn to communicate fluently in English which is not their L1 do so by spending a lot of time in situations where they have to use the language for some real communicative purpose”.*

According to Demetron (1997), *“An antidote to the profusion of skills based activities and artificial language use pervasive in the field of ESL instruction”.* As Bell and Gower (1998) suggested, *“at the very least we listen and speak together, and read and write together”.* Materials should be alluring in terms of appearance, User friendliness and durability. If any can be achieved by providing the activities which involve the situation and their real time conversation (Kumar, 2017). The materials should encourage learners to develop their learning skills and strategies and the activities such as recording of their

material possesses these characteristics then all the learners will readily use the material whole heartedly which will definitely produce the positive results in the classroom. Materials should be flexible also by which we can use that material in many places like a picture can be used to teach parts of speech as well to enhance the spoken skills, even that picture can be used to develop writing skills by the change of instructions. Materials should be authentic also, by which the acquirement will be better and faster and the students feel successful over their achievement because the skills that they acquire make them feel that they can handle the situations in the real life too. Teachers should be very cautious while choosing the materials because the students can be demoralized if the materials are higher than the level of the students (Hall D., 1995).

3. Research Method

The State University of Malang is one of the Indonesian universities which are concerned with the Arabic Language teaching to their students. Hence, this research paper makes an effort to identify the extent of the effectiveness of the instructional materials exploitable to teach Arabic therein.

The research paper is a quantitative evaluative work as it exploits quantitative method to identify some facts about the proper instructional materials for Arabic Language Teaching at the State University of Malang in Indonesia from a widest and comprehensive perspective (Obserne, 1977). As for the evaluative method, it has been adopted for the purpose of rendering an accurate objective ruling, on some approaches, processes and products. Consequently, the areas of strengths and weakness are identifiable to facilitate the adoption of suitable resolutions that can rectify the detected points of weakness and failure (Yusuf, 1962). The researchers distributed copies of the questionnaires to some groups of the community that are connected directly to teaching in the State University of Malang in their efforts to collect data for this research work. The specimens consist of 20 teachers of Arabic Language in the State University of Malang. After that, the researchers analyzed the data through quantitative evaluative method so as to achieve the desired outcome. Furthermore, the researchers, while working on studying of the data of the field survey, adopted a statistical discussion which may be gradually illustrated as follows:

- The researchers were acquainted with adequate information contained in the questionnaires as collected from the specimen and stripped out the number of repeated responses from three options which are: 'I agree', 'To some extent' and 'I disagree', in order to detect the clear and most frequent option from the three possible answers in each item of the questionnaire.
- The researchers relied on the outcome of the stripping to achieve the percentage which reflects the thoughts of the teachers about the instructional materials used for teaching Arabic Language in the State University of Malang in Indonesia.

4. Research Findings

4.1 Application of all types of instructional materials in teaching of Arabic Language (Audio, Visual and Audio-Visual)

Table 2 illustrates the position of the specimen on the expression “Arabic Language Teaching Program provides all required instructional materials (Audio, Visual and Audio-Visual)”

Table 2: Arabic Language Teaching Program provides all required instructional materials (Audio, Visual and Audio-Visual)

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Agree	20	100%
To some extent	0	0%
Disagree	0	0%
Total Number	20	100%

It is clear from the above chart that 100% of the specimen showed their positions that the adopted curriculum provides instructional materials. Thus, these data imply that Arabic Language Teaching Programs are fitted out with instructional materials. Consequently, the outcome of the study discovered Arabic Language Teaching Program is fitted out with all necessary instructional materials; and this is an indication of positive side of for the Arabic Language Teaching in that university.

This research result emerges in conformity with the development of the fields of Arabic Teaching in the university in terms of the provision and use of the instructional materials in the teaching procedure. Obviously, the use of the instructional materials in teaching Arabic Language in the university started diligently since late nineties concurrently with the exploitation of the series of Arabic Language Teaching for Non-Arabic Speakers known as “Arabic for Beginners” in the Arabic Language Teaching Program. With the fact that the aims of those series are directed into the teaching of four language skills which requires seeking assistance of the instructional materials, these programs have been so designed to provide some types of instructional technologies like recording gadgets, cassettes, overhead showing material, video and language laboratory. Since that period, Arabic Language Teaching Programs have been fitted out with various instructional materials, in spite of the fact that these programs have dropped the series of Arabic for Beginners for another teaching series after some years. This is regarded as part of positive sides for Arabic Language Teaching for Non-Arabic Speakers in that university as it supplied means of instructional materials for Arabic Language Teaching therein for the purpose of boosting of its effectiveness inside the university.

4.2 Teachers take interests in exploitation of various instructional materials because it boosts the teaching procedure effectively

Table 3 illustrates the position of the specimen on the statement “Teachers take interest in exploitation of various instructional materials because it boosts the teaching procedure effectively”.

Table 3: The interest in exploitation of various instructional materials

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Agree	15	75%
To some extent	5	25%
Disagree	0	0%
Total Number	20	100%

It is clear from the above chart that 75% from among the specimen have shown their stances that they are interested in using the instructional materials as it helps students on interaction with learning and boosts effectiveness in learning procedure, whereas 25% of the members of the specimen gave proportional answer. This proportional response constitutes minority as the majority of the teachers are interested in the use of instructional materials. The study alluded to the fact that the positive sides for Arabic Language teaching for Non-Arabic Speakers in this university are apparently manifested in the interest of the majority of the teachers in the use of various instructional materials in the teaching process, that is for the purpose of improvement, development and boosting of its effectiveness. As for the negative side, it is obviously seen in the negligence of little number of them in adopting the use of such materials while engaging in teaching Arabic language in the university. It is considered a negative side that should be improved so that all the teachers in the university will be encouraged to develop interest in the use of various instructional materials during the teaching engagement.

The researchers discovered that the knowledge of the teachers about the importance of the instructional materials and their interest in applying them in the teaching activity are two issues that may not collaborate together. Despite the fact that the teachers are fully aware that the instructional materials are instruments that boost the teaching activity effectively, yet that does not necessarily indicate their perfect interest in the adoption of the instructional materials while engaging in teaching activity. That may be as a result of the fact that the use of some materials requires ability to communicate in Arabic Language which is the major thing that some of the teachers of Arabic Language are lacking in this university. Also, the factor of the negligence might erupt from the fact that the use of the instructional materials requires a specific skill as it requires big efforts from the teachers which may enforce extra time of duty from them like subject note preparation and shifting of the materials from one class to another.

4.3 Teachers master the use of the available instructional materials in teaching activity

Table 4 illustrates the extent of the capacity of the teachers in the use of the instructional materials.

Table 4: The extent of the capacity of the teachers on using instructional materials

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Agree	4	20%
To some extent	16	80%
Disagree	0	0%
Total Number	20	100%

It is clear from the above chart that 20% from among the specimen are confident to proclaim the mastery of the application of the instructional materials in the teaching activity, whereas 80% of them gave *average response*, as they are not emphatically sure of their perfect mastery of the materials in the teaching activity.

Meanwhile, the outcome of the research study has discovered that out of the positive sides of the Arabic Language teaching for Non-Arabic Speakers in that university, it is clear that only a little number from among the teachers master the use of the instructional materials in the teaching activity, while on the other hand, it becomes plain that the negative side of it is in the large number among them who have not been able to master its use to some extents. This deficient side requires improvement so as to achieve perfection in teaching Arabic language in that university in a better way.

Hence, the researchers observed that the result reflects a side of deficiency in the provision of the instructional materials in Arabic Language Teaching Programs affiliated to the university. Verily, the provision of the instructional materials was not applied in the training of the teachers practically in the teaching procedure. Therefore, there are a big number of the teachers who ignore the use of the materials in the teaching activity because they do not master the use. In addition, there are a big number of the teachers who are not really assisted by the instructional materials in the presentation lessons effectively as they use the materials wrongly.

On that basis, the result of the research work indicates, on one side, that the teachers master the use of a particular set of the materials only, and not all types. And one another side, they use the instructional materials except that they are not confident of their competent in the perfect application of the instruments accurately. For instance, each teacher uses whiteboard but not all of them are certain of whether the use is accurate as an instructional means for teaching or not. All this implies that they were not trained on the method of the use of the materials in the teaching activity accurately; especially the modern instructional materials among them.

4.4. All the available instructional materials are feasibly usable

Table 5 explains the extent of feasibility of the instructional materials for use:

Table 5: The extent of feasibility of the instructional materials for use

Method Description	Frequency	Percentage
Agree	7	35%
To some extent	13	65%
Disagree	0	0%
Total Number	20	100%

It is clear from the above chart that 35% from among the specimen observed that the available instructional materials are feasibly in good condition for use, while in other hand 65% of them are not confident to answer. Thus, they could not affirm whether the tools of the instructional materials are in good feasible condition for use.

Meanwhile, the outcome of the research study has discovered that most of the available instructional materials in Arabic Language Teaching Programs are feasibly good for use, and this is an indication of positive sides of it. But in the case of its negative side, it is clear that some of them are not in good condition.

Hence, the researchers observed that the obtainable means of instructional materials in Arabic Language Teaching Programs affiliated to that State University of Malang are currently modern as they were acquired since past few years and they were rarely and relatively used.

However, it is good to mention here that this outcome might indicate that the traditional instructional materials like whiteboard, textbooks, pictures and maps may be easily replaced with new copies if they are out of order or invalidated. But modern instructional materials like video, language laboratory and others were not considered as instruments in good condition for perfect use, because if they break down, their maintenance is difficult and expensive. This is due to the fact that the provision of these materials in the programs was associated with a technician who might be readily prepared for such maintenance whenever there is need for that. Likewise, it is due to rareness of the use of these modern types of the instructional materials which may easily be disrupted.

5. Conclusion

After this research study procedure, the two researchers have conclusively arrived at outcomes concerning the positive and negative aspects of the instructional materials in education for the teaching of Arabic language in the State University of Malang. Those aspects are as follow:

The positive aspects are obviously apparent in the fact that Arabic Language Teaching Program in the State University of Malang in Indonesia is fitted out with

various instructional materials (audio and visual). Likewise, the majority of the teachers therein are keenly interested in using those materials in their teaching activities. The purpose of the use is for improvement, development and boosting of the effectiveness of the materials, in addition to the existence of a number of teachers who are expertly well-versed in the exploitation of the instruments. Moreover, most of the instructional materials in the university are still feasible and in good condition.

But the negative aspects are also visibly manifested in the negligence of a little number of them on the use while involving in teaching of Arabic Language there. This is a negative aspect that requires improvement so that it can facilitate the interest of all the teachers in the university to the use of various instructional materials in the teaching activities. Also, there are a great number of other teachers who are not well-versed in the use of the materials to some extent. That is a weak aspect of it which should be improved in order to perfect the teaching of Arabic language in the State University of Malang into a better condition. Likewise, some of the instruments of the instructional materials in the university have been subjected to bad condition and are therefore in need of maintenance.

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